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First-year engineering students' perception of what makes a good study day

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to answer the question: What do first-year engineering students, in a PBL environment, identify as a good study-day and what can be said from a motivational theoretical perspective about this kind of day? The ultimate purpose of the paper is to inform students and teachers within engineering education (EE) about how to spur student motivation. Research into this field is very limited in an EE perspective.

Empirically the study is based on 8 groups individual students' own written descriptions of what they have experienced as being a good study-day.

The analyses identifies indicators of students' individual motivation and discuss what brings the individual students satisfaction and productivity. The study concludes that first year students are mainly motivated by mastering something new and supportive communities.

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INTRODUCTION

This paper reflects an interest in first-year engineering students' perception of what motivates them to study. Research into this field is limited from an engineering education (EE) perspective and yet highly relevant in terms of the final professional quality of engineering students and the retention of the same, not to mention the educational and political awareness these subjects attract (Graham *et al* 2013, Thomas *et al* 2017).

The aim of the paper is to answer the following question: What do first-year engineering students, in a PBL environment, identify as a good study day and what can be said from a motivational theoretical perspective about this kind of day? The ultimate purpose of the paper is to inform students and teachers within EE about how to spur student motivation to, and maintain it at, the highest level possible.

The paper first presents the theoretical framework used to interpret the collected data, then we present the methodology used, and finally we go through the results and discuss them.

1 THEORY ON TOP MOTIVATED YOUNG PEOPLE

1.1 Theory on motivation

Theoretically speaking, motivation has been around for a very long time and been at the centre of attention within many fields, first and foremost psychology, but also within social sciences like business and management (see, for example, Higgins 2011). There is a vast amount of theories and definitions to pick from. Within the educational field, and especially within the engineering education (EE) field, the interest in motivational theories has traditionally been limited. To the extent that interest is now gathering around the motivation of young engineering students, the highly influential theory of self-determination (SD) has been a preferred frame of reference (Trenshaw *et al* 2014, Ohland *et al* 2015, Catz *et al* 2018). This approach underlines the importance of human needs to the attainment of motivation. Three basic needs in particular, namely autonomy, relatedness and competence, should be satisfied in order to bring the individual to a high level of autonomous motivation. SD theory operates with a scale of motivation ranging from not being motivated (a-motivated), through being extrinsically motivated to being intrinsically motivated (see Trenshaw *et al* 2014). In the literature, SD theory has mostly been applied in relation to the education of young people, with the need for autonomy being singled out as the most important need, and only a few studies have been carried out about college students and engineering students (*ibid.*). In these few studies, relatedness needs and competence needs are shown to be of most importance, leading to the conclusion that contextual factors strongly influence what kinds of needs are most important to satisfy (Trenshaw *et al* 2016). And since we are looking at engineering students in a specific PBL context, we would like to utilise a motivational theory a little less generic than SD and a little more focused on the contextual dimensions of motivation.

Hein (2013) is a motivational researcher who seeks to understand motivation from a contextual point of view, focusing on the motivation of creative and highly skilled employees. On the basis of her research, five different motivational types are identified, one of which is not motivated at all, but just there for the money. The other four profiles are motivated either by a work-related cause in itself, by the profession in two different ways or by keeping up a good work-life balance. The theory is, however, developed in a work context and not a higher educational context, so we might be able to use some of the methodology attached, but it makes little sense to regard first-year engineering students as more than potential creative academics.

Katznelson *et al* (2018) and Sørensen *et al* (2013) have conducted research on highly motivated young people inside and outside academia from a contextual point of view, which shows some promise for this study, which is why we will look further into their motivational understanding in the next section.

1.2 Motivation understood as interaction

Katznelson *et al* define their motivational understanding both in terms of what it is not and in terms of what it is:

*“We do not consider motivation as something that is or is not. Something somebody just has and others don’t have. On the contrary, we understand motivation as a dynamic and changeable size, which must be seen and understood in a concrete context and a specific cultural and historical context (Pless *et al.* 2015; Jackson 2006; Lemos 2007). ... [We understand] motivation as something that arises in the encounter between the young people’s experiences, interests and motives for participation, what creates meaning for them, and the cultural practices and frameworks that prevail in the contexts in which they participate.”*

(Katznelson *et al* 2018, pp. 22–23)

According to this line of thought, motivation is understood as an interaction between the single young engineering student and the immediate situation and context at hand.

1.3 Five contexts that motivate young people

As regards top motivated students, Katznelson *et al* (2018) define five contexts in which highly motivated students find their motivation:

Figure 1. Five contexts that motivate young people. Adapted from Katznelson *et al* (2018).

Context no. 1 regards activities or situations in which the student is motivated by learning new knowledge; in context no. 2, the student is motivated by future prospects; in context no. 3, the student is motivated by mastering something new; in context no. 4, the student is motivated by putting an imprint on the world; and in context no. 5, the student is motivated by a community that supports the student.

While going through the results we will qualify these concepts, but first we want to introduce our data collection methods.

2 METHODS FOR COLLECTING DATA AND ANALYSING MOTIVATION AMONGST ENGINEERING STUDENTS

The study is conducted in a project and problem-based learning (PBL) environment at Aalborg University and analyses both individual and group perceptions and reflections on 'what makes a good study day'. The data were collected as part of a bigger research project on group motivation conducted amongst first-year engineering students within two different educational contexts – the combined educational subjects of biochemistry, environmental techniques and biology and the educational subject of techno-anthropology. Eight groups of students were singled out – four groups from each educational context. The groups either volunteered or were asked to participate in the data-gathering events. Three groups volunteered and 5 were asked. Thus, we tried to avoid systematically biased students, and maximised the chances of diversity.

The data comprised observation by videotaping, group interviews and written individual feedback from students.

The empirically data used for the analysis in this paper are entirely based on the individual written feedback, where 33 students from eight groups were asked – within 15 minutes – to write down an answer to the question: ‘what is the best study day you have experienced?’. The question was formulated with inspiration from the research of Hein (2013). She used the same core question (best working day) to make people talk about their motivation for their work.

The individual descriptions of students’ perceptions of a good study day are interpreted and decoded by the two researchers using the five contexts as a theoretical map – first independently and then jointly. Based on these conceptualisations and sense-making, the descriptions are illustrated in a quantitative image. The image map provides a quantitative overview of students’ individual contextual motivation. To provide insight into, and give meaning to, the categories, representative quotes are selected within each category and disseminated. Furthermore, the 33 descriptions of a study day are analysed based on their group belonging. Thus, the eight groups are analysed through the lens of cohesion and diversity, and the two subjects of study mentioned above.

3 RESULTS – WHAT MOTIVATES ENGINEERING STUDENTS?

3.1 Graphical depiction of motivational contexts

Looking at the statements of the 33 students, in aiming to identify the different types of motivational contexts that they adhere to, the following picture emerges:

Figure 2. Graphical depiction of the motivational contexts of the 33 students. Each student adheres to one, two or three motivational types. Most students are motivated by two or three different types. Each ‘|’ constitutes a statement from a student.

As can be seen in the figure, the two motivational types that are most adhered to by the students are being motivated by community support – understood as either the group or the supervisor – and by being able to master or accomplish a specific task or challenge. Twenty-eight students mentioned community support and 23 mentioned mastering something new. Fifteen of the students mentioned being motivated by a clear future goal, seven mentioned acquiring new professional knowledge in itself and one student mentioned being motivated by putting an imprint on the world. Across the eight groups and two educational contexts, some differences could also be identified (see 3.3).

3.2 The five contexts as seen from a qualitative perspective

To give a more qualitative picture of the five different motivational contexts we have gathered some quotes that illustrate what the five contexts are about.

3.2.1 Examples of knowledge that motivates

Being motivated by the subject itself was mentioned by seven students. Typical comments:

"The ideas flew through the room"

"... [we had] a day where we found a really specific and exciting position within our main topic."

3.2.2 Examples of future perspectives that motivate

Six students mentioned being motivated by having clear long-term goals, linked to the goal of the project:

"... we got the project on track. We then agreed... on a problem statement ..."

"for the first time we had a common goal and mission, which was highly motivating"

Some of the other 15 students in this category underlined that not only clear long-term goals but also clear agendas and a clear direction of discussions as well as actually reaching a goal contributed to having a good study day:

"... Good discussions about potential ways one could go with the project ..."

"You come home and feel that we as a group have moved a good distance closer to the goal."

"... the days when we know what to do and have a purpose."

"... to reach a goal that we all agreed on."

3.2.3 Examples of mastering something new that motivates

What the students mention they master are different elements of the PBL process. Two students mentioned mastering a method for structuring the work process – the process of brainstorming and delimiting a problem formulation. Another two mentioned being able to work alone at home and accomplish what they set out to accomplish. One student mentioned being able to solve a difficult professional challenge in the lab. Eighteen out of the 23 students in this category talked about different aspects of being productive – finding a good balance between working hard and having fun, getting a

lot done, securing a good working flow, being well prepared and efficient or accomplishing what was planned:

"There was a good balance between serious work and breaks"

"... a constant flow and a good productivity."

"I liked that we were so structured and got an effective job done."

Five students talked about succeeding in carrying out collaborative work:

"... we [have] had many days where we do not really know where we are going, then it can be really nice to suddenly feel that you are moving forward ... if you finally agree on something."

3.2.4 Examples of putting an imprint on the world that motivates

A single student made a remark that pointed in the direction of being motivated by putting an imprint on the world:

"I felt that I myself was totally turned on by the project, as we found a subtopic that was relatively groundbreaking in the field of the study, and generally just interesting."

3.2.5 Examples of community support that motivates

When the students talked about community support, they pointed to different aspects of social support. One thing that motivates is when the supervisor or the group as a whole is enthusiastic about what is going on in the group collaboration. Four students mentioned acknowledgement from the supervisor and three students referred to when everybody in the group was happy. A specific kind of happiness arose when everyone in the group contributed and "pulled in the same direction". Eight students mentioned this particular trait of a motivating group collaboration. Nine students underlined that a well-structured group collaboration that supports each other's activities and/or helps solve challenging professional issues is very motivating. One of these students said:

"On this one day, the feeling of perdition disappeared and all the frustrations were hidden away when we saw what each other was really capable of ..."

Social cosiness – having fun while working together – is also a high scorer, and was mentioned by seven students:

"... it is also those day, when it really has been fun to meet and work together – emphasising work."

Finally, five students underlined the creation of a generally nice atmosphere in the group as being very motivating.

"It was awesome, that we had created an environment where it was allowed to ask stupid questions and where we could help each other ... a feeling that we together improve each other."

3.3 Looking at the group context

Looking at the 33 students from a group context perspective it is noticeable that the group context has an influence on the ways in which each single student is motivated. Following the individual analysis it is not surprising that 'mastering something new' and 'being supported by community' also dominate the analysis on a group level. However, it is not random how these motivational contexts are mentioned within each group. There seems to be a pattern where group members either highlight 'mastering something new' or 'being supported by community' as the dominating motivational context, except for two groups that have a somewhat scattered outcome. Among the six groups that align internally, there is an even balance between groups focusing on 'mastering something new' and groups focusing on 'being supported by community'. The groups thus reflect diverse values and underlying motivational context connections, which seem to have developed within each group as a dominating motivational context.

Looking at the groups from a subject perspective there seems to be a tendency for techno-anthropology groups to highlight 'being supported by community' as the primary motivational context, whereas biochemistry, environmental techniques and biology students have a tendency to highlight 'mastering something new'.

4 WHAT CAN WE LEARN FROM THIS AS EDUCATORS?

Returning to the initial question – what do first-year engineering students, in a PBL environment, identify as a good study day and what can be said from a motivational theoretical perspective about this kind of day? – the analysis of the 33 students' answers to this question show, through analysis according to Katznelson *et al.*'s motivational contexts, that students are most motivated by a 'community that motivates', which to a large extent can be related to collaboration processes and social relations within the group. But also, the ability to 'master something new' comes out with a very high score, which relates mostly to the students being productive and efficient. This is interesting as the students are first-year students and thus newbies in a PBL learning environment that implements a student-centred learning method. This method requires a high degree of self-determination, which it seems the students relate to, in the form of pursuing productiveness. Fewer students mention 'future perspectives' as a motivational context – e.g. obtaining a clear problem formulation or the experience of working towards a clear direction or even just a clear agenda. The feeling of structure and perhaps some degree of security seems important, as a PBL process might be experienced as an uncertain way of learning compared to a more traditional teacher-centred approach, which most students have been used to from high school. Less than a quarter of the students are motivated by the engineering subject knowledge itself. This may seem surprising, but for the first semester the PBL projects are new and the semester does have learning outcomes that contain PBL competences that the students must acquire. Only one student gave an answer that pointed in the direction of being motivated by putting an imprint on the world. Again,

the context is first year students in a new learning environment, indicating that learning resources are focused on these matters.

The analysis of answers from students across the eight groups shows a balance between groups focusing on ‘mastering something new’ and groups focusing on ‘being supported by community’. This indicates the development of norms within the groups in regard to which motivational contexts are considered important. Looking at the groups from a subject perspective, there seems to be a tendency for techno-anthropology groups to highlight ‘being supported by community’ as the primary motivational context, whereas biochemistry, environmental techniques and biology students have a tendency to highlight ‘mastering something new’. Based on this, it may be possible to formulate a hypothesis that different academic subjects attract different students who are motivated by different external contexts or that the academic contexts themselves are biased towards one or other form of motivational context.

This study into motivational contexts indicates that first-year engineering students from a PBL environment, and based on their own descriptions of what they consider to be a good study day, are motivated by collaboration processes and social relations, and further the feeling of mastering something new, more than by future perspectives or the subject knowledge itself. This is of importance for us as supervisors and teachers in the first year to know and take into consideration when we aim to motivate our students.

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